

HISTORY OF NAVRUZ AND ITS FIRST INTERPRETATIONS IN LITERATURE

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Abstract: Navruz holiday, which has a thousand-year history, is still alive today. It is one of our national values that has its place not only in history but also in literature. This article describes the long history of Nowruz and its first appearance in literature. In particular, myths and legends about the origin of Nowruz are covered.

Key words: Nowruz holiday, new day, tradition, historical evidence, treats, abundance, crops, spring holiday.

Nowruz holiday in Central Asia, Iran and Afghanistan during the Achaemenid period widespread in the 6th century BC. So, we can assume that the history of Nowruz is equal to 25-30 centuries. From the beginning of Nowruz, it plays the main role of the year. And it is called "new day". According to the Zoroastrian calendar, on the first day of February, "Little Nowruz" began, and on the sixth day, "Big Nowruz" was organized. Regardless of when and how Navroz is celebrated, it has been introduced on a scientific basis. Sun's entry into Hamal sign, the days begin to lengthen, the revival of nature is accepted as N Euroz. Nowruz coincided with the beginning of Farvordin month according to the old solar calendar. Beruni in his work "Relics of Ancient Nations" stated that "Little Nowruz" lasts until the sixth day of the month of Farvordin. The historical information about the emergence of Spring and Labor Day has undergone various changes over time and has reached us wrapped in myths and legends. Most of such legends connect the creation of Navrozi world with the legendary name of Jamshid.

According to Abulqasim Firdavsi in his work "Shohnoma", Navroz is associated with the name of Jamshid. [1.1] In ancient times, there was a king named Jamshid, who, in order to do good to the country, trained people in professions, built various palaces, revealed the secrets of medicine, and created gardens. Finally, one day he made a throne and ascended to the sky.

The great poet interpreted it in beautiful verses as follows:

He built one throne, all of it

Shukuhi Kayoniy, the decoration is a gem.

"Let the giant fly away," was the order.

When the throne was raised, the sky fell.

To the throne of judgment of all people,

The world is happy.

Jamshid scatters gold and jewels,

This day is called the New Year holiday. [2.1]

The work "Navruznama" by the great scientist and humanitarian poet of the East, Umar Khayyam, tells about our long history, the origin of the Navruz holiday, and related traditions of our ancestors.

Umar Khayyam describes the development of the solar calendar and its history in his work "Navruznama". According to this calendar, he explained how the kings of Iran determined the day of Nowruz and how they spent the holiday with historical evidence.

The month of Farvardin - "farvardin" - its meaning is the heavens, and this month is the beginning of the growth of plants. This month belongs to Hamal.

Urdbikhisht month - this month is called Urdbikhisht, in this month the world is heavenly with its blueness. In this month, the sun is in the sign of Saur according to its true rotation.

Khurdad month - feeds people with wheat, barley and fruits. The sun will be in the sign of Javza this month.

The month of Tir - this month is called "Tir" because in this month they distribute wheat, barley and other things. The sun will be in Cancer.

The month of Murdod - gave soil, that is, it gave fruits and vegetables ripened in it. The sun will be in Asad.

The month of Shahrivar is called Shahrivar, because it is the month of income, that is, the income of kings corresponds to this month. The sun will be in Azro (Sunbula).

The month of mercy is called the month of mercy because it is the month of friendship between people and they share together all the ripe fruits and other things and what has touched their share. The sun will be in Mezon this month.

The month of Obon means that the rains that started in this month increase the water and people water their crops. The sun will be in Aqrab this month.

Ozar month - In this month, the weather starts to cool and the need for fire appears, that is, it is the month of fire. The sun will be in Sagittarius this month.

Day month - The reason why this month is called "day" is because it is fierce and the earth is far from turning green in this month. The sun will be in Jadi.

Bahman month means like that. Because this month is cold and dry like that month. The sun will be sunny this month.

Isfandarmuz month - this month is called Isfandarmuz, that is, fruit trees and plants start to turn green in this month. The sun reaches the last zodiac sign this month.

From this day, farmers put plows in the ground, start sowing, and plant the seeds of blessings for a bountiful harvest. [3.2]

In this work, Omar Khayyam appears not only as an ethnographer, historian, scientist, but also as a learned physician. For example, it has been shown that in ancient times, sumac dish was often prepared from barley and wheat grass, and that sumac made from barley and wheat grass is a cure for many diseases.

Alisher Navoi in his work "Tarihi muluki ajam" expresses this event as follows: Jamshid built an unprecedented and incredible tall building called "Chikhil minar"... "this building was finished, the world gathered peace and blessings and news, and then determination flourished. At that time, The sun worshiped the religious rabbi and put him on the throne in the building. justice spread the sound and sound of justice to the world, and the horse of the day called Navroz.

If we look at the information left by Beruni, in it, the New Year holiday is also associated with Jamshid: "When Jamshid made a cart for himself, he went out on the cart that day, demons and the devils lifted him into the air and took him from Dunbovan (Mount Damovand) to Babylon one day. When people saw this wonderful event, they celebrated Eid on that day and imitating Jamshid, they flew on ropes. "

Our great grandfather Khwaja Ali Hakim al-Tirmizi's "Navro`znama" contains the following views about the arrival of Navruz.

" If Nowruz falls on Sunday, there will be abundance and famine. The crop yield is good, it will be abundant. Crops should be sown earlier. If Navruz falls on Monday, there will be a feast and there will be many delicacies. It rains a lot, the grain yield is average. Earthquakes occur in some places. Polished crops will not be good. But wheat is sweet.

If Navruz falls on Tuesday, there will be a lot of joy that year. Blessings are given to people and blessings to all creatures. Crops should be sown early. Fruits are plentiful and prices are low. But there are disagreements between people.

If Nowruz falls on Wednesday, there may be a shortage, but it will soon be over. Police will be flooded, grain will be threshed. Insects are also killed. Trading is at its peak.

If Nowruz falls on Thursday, there will be a lot of precipitation. Good luck to kings. Craftsmen's work will be blessed. Trade will develop, but lies and ill will will rise among the people.

If Nowruz falls on Friday, the people will achieve joy and prosperity. It rains a lot, winter is long and cold. The prices are cheap, the benefits are plentiful.

If Navruz falls on Saturday, you will have to endure some hunger. It rains a lot, the autumn crops are good, and the fruits yield less. The cold will be severe, the winter will be long .

By the Middle Ages, Nowruz holiday has developed further, became public. Although some individuals opposed the celebration of Navro, the hard-working people continued to celebrate it , and all kinds of poems were written about it. songs were created. After all, Navroz passed through several stressful stages and reached us safely. Nowruz holiday despite all pressures after it was not celebrated, some "patriotic" kings and emirs decided to organize it as a holiday in the following centuries.

Before the introduction of Islam, the customs of Navroz, which belonged to ordinary people, are also noteworthy. On the day of the holiday, people give each other sugar and sweets (in the sense that your life will be sweet), sprinkle each other with water (in the sense that this year there will be a lot of water and a good harvest) and other customs are common. In the following centuries, customs such as cleaning the courtyards, planting greenery and flowers, visiting parents, relatives and friends, and visiting the graves of the deceased became a part of Navroz holiday.

In different places of Uzbekistan, Navruz holiday was celebrated in different ways, and this joy lasted from several days to a week or even a month.

Nowruz was mainly celebrated in special parks and hills. On the day of the holiday, trumpets and trumpets were played early in the morning, heralds invited people to the holiday. Riders, wrestlers, clowns, bakhshis, singers, players-dancers showed their performances to the visitors of the holiday. Nowruz has always been celebrated in such an upbeat manner.

So, regardless of where and when Navruz is celebrated, it has reached us, and we celebrate it in a very high mood..

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